

ENVIRONMENTAL RISK ASSESSMENT FOR PAMBUKOVICA DAM PROJECT IN SERBIA – A CASE STUDY

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Abstract: *The Kolubara River basin, located in Western Serbia, is marked by unfavourable water regimes and therefore has been hit multiple times by floods in the past. The complexity of the issue was emphasized by the floods that occurred in 2014, when the local communities, industry, and infrastructure along the Kolubara basin suffered extensive damage. In light of this event, Pambukovica Dam has been proposed as one of the ways to prevent future disasters of a similar scale. Hence, the required studies were commissioned for the actualization of such a project, amongst which is an Environmental Impact Assessment Study (in line with Serbian legislation). Pambukovica Dam (named after the nearby village in western Serbia) is planned to be situated on the Ub River. Its construction and operations pose several environmental risks (all of which mitigation measures have been outlined for), including air pollution, noise during construction, disruption of groundwater soil layers, improper surplus material disposal, threats to biodiversity and landscape changes. Technical monitoring of the Dam includes geodetic, physical and visual monitoring. Overall, the Project brings a number of benefits for the local community, but it also faces certain challenges that must be carefully managed.*

Keywords: Environmental Risk Assessment, Dam, Environmental impact, Environmental monitoring, Environmental Protection

1. INTRODUCTION

The Kolubara River basin, located in Western Serbia, is marked by unfavourable water regimes and therefore has been hit multiple times by floods in the past [1]. Ensuring protection from floods for the valleys situated in the basin has historically been a critical problem, as outlined in the Preliminary Flood Risk Assessment conducted in 2012, wherein the Kolubara river basin was labelled as significant with national ramifications in the Republic of Serbia [2]. The complexity of the issue was emphasized by the floods that occurred in 2014, when the local communities, industry, infrastructure and natural resources along the Kolubara basin suffered extensive damage [1]. In light of this tragic event, the 2018 Kolubara River Basin Catchment Study by the Institute for Water Management “Jaroslav Černi” put forward the Pambukovica Dam as one of the ways to prevent future catastrophes of a similar scale [3]. Hence, the required studies were commissioned for the actualization of such a project, amongst which is a Feasibility Study (prepared by “Energoprojekt Hidroinženjering”), Environmental Impact Assessment Study (in accordance with Serbian legislation), Conceptual Design, Design for Construction Permit and Baseline Biodiversity Surveys [4].

It is important to note that the Republic of Serbia is vigorously working to align its environmental protection legislation with that of the European Union. This process includes adopting new regulations and modifying existing ones to fulfill the criteria of EU standards. Essential areas of focus encompass air quality, water protection and waste management. Serbia has taken many vital steps to do so, but the harmonization process is yet to be finished and demands constant engagement.

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The aim is to ensure that Serbian laws in the field of ecology are completely in line with EU directives, which will aid in enhancing environmental quality and sustainable development in the country [5].

Most recently, the Law on Environmental Impact Assessment (“Official Gazette of RS”, No. 94/2024) and the Law on Strategic Environmental Impact Assessment (“Official Gazette of RS”, No. 94/2024) came into force on December 6, 2024. These two laws were introduced to accomplish better alignment of local regulations with relevant EU directives in the field of environmental protection – Directive 2011/92/EU, amended by Directive 2014/52/EU, and Directive 2001/42/EC. Their implementation is forecasted to add a new dimension to the regulation of environmental protection, with the goal of updating and strengthening protection measures, motivating the general public to become more engaged, raising environmental awareness and making administration more efficient [6].

The purpose of this paper is to present a case study for Pambukovica Dam Project in Serbia. Aside from a general Project and location description, an environmental risk assessment will be conducted – with a focus on potential impacts, mitigation measures and environmental impact monitoring during dam operations. In the Discussion and Conclusion section both benefits and challenges of the Project will be listed in detail.

2. THE CASE STUDY

2.1 Description of location, project and main alternatives

Pambukovica Dam (named after the nearby village in western Serbia) is planned to be situated on the Ub River around 21 km upstream from the confluence to Tamnava River, which is 15km west from the town of Ub. Location of the Dam is within the boundaries of the cadastral municipalities of Pambukovica, Slatina, Raduša and Gola Glava [7,8].

The design prepared by “Energoprojekt Hidroinženjering” includes construction of a 30.5 m tall earth embankment dam (Phase 1 of the Project) on the Ub River, as well as an irrigation system (Phase 2 of the Project, now envisioned to commence in parallel with completion of Phase 1) within the Ub River Valley. The dam will be multifunctional - containing a total reservoir volume of 8.15 million m³. Its purpose consists of: flood control, irrigation of approximately 2,225 ha, sediment retention and keeping a guaranteed ecological flow in reservoir and downstream river. Approximate time required for building the dam is 2-3 years, taking into account the amount of work and determining the dynamics of project execution. Estimated dam lifetime is 80 years [9].

The main Project solution alternatives were discussed in the Environmental Impact Assessment Study in terms of reservoir concept, dam type, location, fish path and Project/No-Project, both from an environmental and social standpoint. The multipurpose reservoir was chosen instead of a retention structure, because of its core characteristics (flood protection capabilities, irrigation, ecological flow), maintaining environmental balance and groundwater levels and helping afforestation, as well as supporting the local economy by supporting local agriculture, industry, and household water use. The selected earth-fill dam option supports local communities by providing a stable water supply for agricultural and industrial needs. It introduces financial benefits by boosting local employment, utilizing local resources, and enhancing infrastructure. The design is incorporated well with the natural environment, does not disrupt the local ecosystem as much, and is technically feasible, economically justifiable, and not difficult for upkeep. The chosen site is adequate both in terms of geography and geology, especially because of the narrow valley, which ensures lower construction costs and minimises the land expropriation required, thus decreasing displacement of local residents. When it comes to the selected No Fish Path Solution, one problem is that this will decrease the natural connectivity of the river along its length, and while present fish species are predicted to adapt without

the need for a fish passage, some species will require new habitats to be developed. Land acquisition could possibly negatively affect the lives of people, and therefore measures are being implemented, in order to ensure just compensation. Nonetheless, the chosen solutions reflect an approach designed to accommodate the needs of all the relevant parties in the Project [9].

2.2 Environmental impact

The major environmental impacts of the Pambukovica Dam Project are summarized below for several key aspects [9]:

- 1) Air pollution – construction work would cause temporary air pollution via dust and emissions of nitrogen oxides and carbon monoxide from machinery and trucks. However, there is no expected air pollution during dam operations (i.e., little to no emissions).
- 2) Noise and vibration – Significant sources of noise and vibration during the construction phase include blasting and drilling work, as well as excavators, bulldozers and trucks. Throughout the operational phase, the dam will not produce significant noise and vibrations. Similarly, the pre-construction stage will consist of solely minor preparation work, and the decommissioning phase is expected to have effects akin to those during construction, but for a limited time.
- 3) Alteration of water flow and disturbance of soil layers – This occurs during construction as a result of utilizing heavy machinery, material storage and excavation. Soil contamination can occur as a result of mismanagement of building materials. Furthermore, deforestation can lead to erosion. During dam operations, the reservoir may raise groundwater levels in nearby areas, and change natural hydrological trends. In the decommissioning phase, dismantling infrastructure and draining the reservoir could make the soil unstable.
- 4) Unsafe disposal of surplus material - The construction of the Pambukovica Dam will require a vast quantity of natural resources (i.e., clay, sand, gravel and rock). If not properly managed, the unsafe disposal of about 225,000 surplus material (as a result of excavation work) could impact land stability and water quality.
- 5) Waste and wastewater - During construction, there is a risk from hazardous waste (i.e., oils, lubricants, paints, and solvents). Wastewater will arise from construction works, worker facilities, and stormwater runoff. If mismanaged, these waste streams could result in soil and water contamination, adversely impacting local ecosystems and public health.
- 6) Damage to cultural heritage - Excavation, blasting and heavy machinery traffic may potentially disturb or damage both documented and undiscovered cultural assets if not handled adequately. Vibrations arising from construction and transport could leave a negative effect on structures in the vicinity.
- 7) Emergency scenario - In the hypothetical scenario of a dam failure (because of erosion, overtopping throughout heavy floods, or other structural obstacles) there could be severe consequences for downstream settlements, infrastructure and the environment. Even the town of Ub could be affected.
- 8) Landscape and visual changes – Changes to the landscape will be visible as a result of construction activities. The most evident alteration will be the building of a reservoir, which will fundamentally change the natural appearance of the Ub River valley. A water body will replace agricultural land and trees.
- 9) Changes to the river system – This includes alteration of river flow and amount of water, water quality concerns (risk of nutrient build-up in the reservoir, which could lead to algae growth and reduced water quality downstream), sediment accumulation and riverbed changes, erosion and habitat fragmentation, as well as localized erosion underneath the dam.
- 10) Threat to biodiversity – This encompasses habitat destruction, limitations to fish movement (the dam being a physical barrier), disturbing wildlife via construction activities and water quality and flow alterations.

2.3 Mitigation measures

Below is a summary of the major ecological risk mitigation measures covered in the Environmental Impact Assessment Study for Pambukovica Dam Project [9]:

- 1) Air pollution – To mitigate this risk, pre-construction monitoring, dust control, emissions reduction (through utilizing contemporary, well-maintained machines with emission controls) and monitoring and management measures will be implemented.
- 2) Noise and vibration – Throughout pre-construction monitoring, noise measurements will be done before construction commences to determine starting conditions and ensure conformity with Serbian regulations. When it comes to the actual construction stage, noisy operations will be limited to daytime hours, modern and regularly maintained equipment will be utilized to decrease noise and vibration, traffic intensity will be adjusted, temporary noise barriers will be placed near sensitive areas if required and controlled blasting techniques will be deployed with safe distances maintained from sensitive receptors. Daily noise and vibration monitoring during project works will be done close to sensitive receptors.
- 3) Alteration of water flow and disturbance of soil layers – During the construction stage, negative soil and groundwater effects will be reduced by stopping equipment leaks, safely storing hazardous materials, handling excavated materials appropriately, implementing erosion prevention techniques, and monitoring groundwater levels to ensure compliance with Serbian regulations. During dam operations, the fertility of the soil will be enhanced through irrigation, and erosion will be managed using protective vegetation and embankments.
- 4) Unsafe disposal of surplus material – Important measures encompass planning extraction and rehabilitation areas dedicated specifically to borrow pits and quarries, realization of reuse and recycling strategies to reduce waste generation, determining transport routes and timetables to lower traffic and emissions, monitoring water use from the Ub River and ensuring all operations are in line with ecological legislation.
- 5) Waste and wastewater – To mitigate risks arising from this, the following measures will be implemented: creating a Waste Management Plan, wastewater treatment, sanitary facilities, stormwater control and sediment management.
- 6) Damage to cultural heritage – The following mitigation measures will be implemented: site surveys, vibration monitoring near sensitive cultural sites, training for construction personnel to raise historical awareness and coordination with cultural authorities.
- 7) Emergency scenario – The main measures include an Early Warning System, alarm levels & response, evacuation plans, raising social awareness, institutional coordination and annual updates.
- 8) Landscape and visual changes – Deforestation will be minimized as much as possible, and new trees will be planted in zones along the reservoir banks to make the landscape look visually appealing and natural. This will also aid in slowing down erosion.
- 9) Changes to the river system – Mitigation measures include pollution control and water quality monitoring, sediment management, erosion control and land restoration, improving river connectivity and monitoring & adaptive management.
- 10) Threat to biodiversity – Mitigation measures would involve habitat offsetting and restoration, creating a Biodiversity Management Plan, protecting species of fish, long-term monitoring and adaptive management, invasive species control and stakeholder engagement.

2.4 Environmental impact monitoring during dam operations

Environmental monitoring is carried out to control the impact of the Project on the environment, as well as to verify the effectiveness of measures implemented to prevent and reduce harmful impacts arising from its implementation. Environmental monitoring is carried out by systematically measuring, testing and assessing indicators of environmental conditions and pollution, which includes

monitoring natural factors, i.e., changes in the conditions and characteristics of the environment, namely: air, water, soil, forests, biodiversity, flora and fauna, climate elements, noise, waste, early warning of accidents with monitoring and assessment of the development of environmental pollution, etc. There is an obligation to engage authorized organizations to perform professional monitoring tasks. Measurements of environmental parameters are carried out at representative measuring points [9].

The determination of the position and representativeness of the measuring points is carried out by a person authorized for the appropriate type of measurement, based on the requirements and prescribed measurement methods, depending on the parameters being monitored, and in accordance with the regulations regulating the measurements in question. Water quality testing should be conducted four times a year on at least three characteristic profiles along the length of the reservoir, as well as at different depths along the profile and at one location downstream of the dam. Groundwater quality should be monitored in two piezometers, one on the left and one on the right side of the reservoir, twice a year. Sediment quality will be tested once a year using accredited methods by a laboratory authorized for these types of measurements [9].

Technical monitoring of the Pambukovica Dam is divided into several categories, which differ from each other according to the methods used [9]:

- 1) Geodetic monitoring;
- 2) Physical monitoring;
- 3) Visual monitoring;
- 4) Other forms of monitoring.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The Pambukovica Dam Project is expected to bring a multitude of benefits. Constructing the flood alleviation dam will support enhanced water and flood management in the Ub river basin and finally help with better control of flood occurrences in the Kolubara river basin, reducing and minimizing adverse effects of floods in the zones which have been hit in the past. Operation of the multipurpose reservoir in Phase 2 of the Project will make water available for irrigation in the area for a maximum of 2,225 ha, providing support to local agricultural activities. Throughout dam operations, the reservoir will help provide a consistent ecological flow during times of drought, which will be beneficial for the aquatic ecosystem downstream of the dam. Impoundment of the reservoir leads to a functional advantage for certain animals. Amongst these animals are birds that are dependent on water, as well as bats and fish that will have the possibility to use the water body as a refuge when the Ub River upstream of the dam is undergoing drought conditions. Construction activities may potentially boost local employment and skillset. By minimizing the extent of damage from floods and enabling irrigation throughout drought periods, operation of the reservoir will ensure local and regional development.

However, given the scale and multidimensional nature of this Project, it also faces a number of challenges, which make Environmental Impact Assessment difficult. A major concern lies in ensuring accurate baseline data for hydrology, sediment transport, and biodiversity, which is critical for predicting and mitigating long-term ecological impacts. The project's intended functions—flood control, irrigation, and ecological flow maintenance—require careful balancing, especially as dam operations can disrupt natural flow regimes and aquatic ecosystems downstream. Sediment accumulation, loss of habitat, and potential impacts on water quality further complicate the assessment. Additionally, evaluating cumulative impacts from existing and future infrastructure in the Ub River basin, alongside uncertainties posed by climate change, adds to the complexity. Social aspects such as land use changes, public engagement, and compliance with both Serbian regulations

and international standards also present significant obstacles, particularly in ensuring meaningful stakeholder consultation and effective long-term monitoring.

The realization of the Pambukovica Dam Project would be a turning point for the local community and environment. The significance of its execution is reflected in how this case study covered aspects such as its location, technical details, environmental risks, mitigation measures and environmental impact monitoring. It is critical to ensure that the Project is planned and implemented adequately - a goal which environmental risk assessment absolutely contributes to. Only in this way is it possible to ensure that the right steps are taken on every stage of the Project – be it preparatory works, construction, operational phase or decommissioning phase. Public health, safety and ecological concerns should be at the forefront of any venture of this scale – and the Environmental Impact Assessment Study exists precisely to foresee all potential impacts and plan the appropriate measures for each, whilst taking into account both temporal and spatial challenges of overseeing their implementation in practice.

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